

THE ROLE OF ZOONYMS IN FRENCH METEOROLOGICAL PAREMIOLOGY

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Annotation: The significance of paremiological units lies in their ability to reflect life experience, enduring lessons, traditions, and national-cultural characteristics, as well as in their close connection with national mentality and folk culture. Thus, through these units, it is possible not only to study a particular language, but also to explore the culture, social life, and traditions of the people who speak that language. Paremias reveal a nation's beliefs, values, perceptions of the relationship between humans and nature, its identity, and social life. Therefore, they are considered an important phenomenon of linguoculturology.

Key words: zoonym, figurative expression, phraseological units, figurative meaning, meteorology;

Among paremiological units, proverbs and sayings containing zoonym components stand out for their particular role in reflecting a people's national identity, culture, traditions, and life experience. Paremiological units involving zoonyms constitute an important part of paremiology, as they reveal the people's attitudes toward the animal world, as well as their beliefs and customs associated with it. Moreover, such units frequently employ animals metaphorically to represent human character traits and qualities.

The linguistic and cultural specificities of phraseological units with zoonym components have also been studied by scholars worldwide. For instance, researcher D.A. Tishkina conducts a comparative analysis of zoonym-based phraseological units in English and Russian. Likewise, researchers E. Milburn and T. Worren examine the literal and figurative meanings of such phraseological units¹. In this regard, substantial research has also been carried out in Uzbek linguistics. In particular, researcher G.E. Khakimova examines phraseological units containing zoonyms from structural and semantic perspectives. S.B. Abdullayeva, in turn, studies the linguo-pragmatic features of these units in characterizing human traits.²

Today, interest in this field of linguistics is steadily increasing. In this study, we have also attempted to examine the role of zoonyms in French meteorological paremias and to analyze their specific linguo-cultural and semantic features. Since the emergence of humankind, the relationship between humans and nature has been an inseparable part of social life. This relationship is, in turn, reflected in language. Meteorological proverbs and sayings can be cited as an example of this. Meteorological paremias refer to proverbs and sayings related to natural phenomena such as rain, wind, fog, snow, and storms.

In France, as in many other countries, agricultural sectors such as farming and livestock breeding have long been developed. Therefore, meteoronyms occupy an important place in the social life of the population in this region. French meteorological paremias reflect the French people's unique worldview, culture, traditions, and customs related to the relationship between

¹ Milburn Evelyn, Warren Tessa. Idioms shows effects of meaning relatedness and dominance similar to those seen for ambiguous words// psychonomic bulletin and review. – Springer, 2019. – Pp.591-598.

² Abdullayeva S.B. Insonni xaraterlashda zoonim komponentli frazeologik birliklardagi lingvopragmatik xususiyatlar (ingliz va o'zbek tillari misolida): Filol. fan. fals. dokt. ...diss. – Samarqand, 2022. – 148 b.

humans and nature. By studying such proverbs and sayings, it is possible to understand the significance of meteoronyms in the social and cultural life of the French people, as well as their specific values in this regard.

For example: “S’il neige à la Saint-Onésime, la récolte est à l’abîme.” In French culture, 16 February is the feast day of Saint Onésime. Snowfall on this day is considered a bad omen in French agricultural tradition. Generally, snow and rain meteoronyms are regarded as symbols of abundance and prosperity due to the presence of water; however, in this proverb, “la neige” (snow) acquires a negative meaning. If we translate the proverb into Uzbek, it would read: “If it snows on Saint Onésime’s day, the harvest will be ruined.”

The presence of zoonyms as components in French meteorological proverbs and sayings is a frequent phenomenon. In French meteorological paremias, a wide range of zoonyms appear as components, including domestic animals: le coq, le mouton, la poule, la souris, le paon, la vache, le chien, le cheval, la brebis, le chat, le boeuf, l’âne, l’abeille, le lapin, le canard, le porc; wild animals: le loup, le serpent, la couleuvre, la vipère, la chauve-souris, l’ours; birds: l’hirondelle, le huard, la mouette, le paon, la pie, le pigeon, le pintade, le pivert, la grive, le coucou, la corneille, la cigogne, la chouette, la caille, l’alcyon; insects: l’escargot, la mouche, le papillon, l’araignée; and fish: le huard, la lotte, le congre, la carpe, le poisson, la baleine, le requin, le marsouin.

The occurrence of zoonyms in French meteorological paremias plays an important role in forming linguo-cultural units based on French folk meteorology, reflecting traditional ways of understanding and interpreting nature. These paremias represent empirical knowledge formed through observation of nature. In them, animals serve as indicators of weather conditions. The knowledge of the French people, based on observing nature through animal behavior and using it to interpret and predict weather, is clearly reflected in these expressions.

For example, in the proverb “Marsouins sautant, annoncent le vent”, the movement of porpoises is interpreted as a sign of wind. This is an example of *météorologie populaire*. Similarly, in “Les mouches et les taons, piquent avant le mauvais temps”, the behavior of flies and horseflies is associated with approaching bad weather. In “Cris de mouette, signe de tempête”, the loud cries of seagulls indicate an approaching storm.

In conclusion, it can be stated that French meteorological paremias with zoonym components represent an important tool for studying the social life, traditions, and customs of a given people. These linguistic units are a kind of treasure that encapsulates the knowledge and experience accumulated by each nation over centuries, and their continued use in contemporary speech demonstrates their significant role in transmitting experience and knowledge from generation to generation.

The use of zoonyms in meteorological paremias enriches these expressions and increases their expressiveness and significance. These French proverbs and sayings were formed on the basis of farmers’ and rural communities’ practical experience and observations, and the empirical knowledge embedded in them reflects traditions and understandings related to the relationship between humans and nature.

During the analysis, it was revealed that meteorological paremias with zoonym components create both positive and negative semantic microfields within a cultural context.

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